

THE SOLIDIFICATION PROCESS DURING PRESSURE CASTING SiC AND AL₂O₃

REINFORCED AL-4.5%Cu METAL MATRIX COMPOSITES

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Abstract

Composites of 40 v/o 20 micron diameter alumina (Fiber FP) and 140 micron diameter Silicon Carbide (SCS-2) fibers have been infiltrated with a molten Al-4.5%Cu alloy by a pressure casting process. The resultant matrix microstructures are examined and interpreted.

For solidification experiments in which a cooling rate is chosen to produce dendrite arm spacings of nearly the same magnitude as the interfiber spacing in the preform, the dendritic structure normally observed in the unreinforced alloy is no longer definable in sections transverse to the fiber axis. Solute-poor regions lie in the center of the interfiber spaces and the matrix becomes richer in solute in regions near the fiber surface. The eutectic phase fields, being the last to solidify, are found primarily on the fiber surfaces. Microsegregation is significantly reduced in specimens in which cooling rates were chosen to produce dendrite arm spacings much larger than the interfiber distance. Underlying mechanisms are discussed.

Introduction

One of the prime obstacles to the introduction of metal matrix composites into practical applications is the low state of the art of consolidation. The two principle problems facing the developer of consolidation processes are:

1) Poor wetting of the reinforcement (fiber) by the molten matrix alloy and

2) Degradation of the fiber strength through chemical reaction during consolidation [1,2]. Liquid metal infiltration processing promises to be the least expensive method of composite consolidation providing the problems mentioned above can be overcome. The poor wettability between most fibers and aluminum alloys results in a negative capillary pressure that must be overcome during infiltration. Once the molten alloy begins to infiltrate the preform, viscous drag effects result in a pressure drop that must be overcome. Relationships describing each of these pressure drops can be found in references 3 and 4. These pressure drops can best be overcome by the application of hydrostatic pressure during infiltration. Further, the temperature of the fiber preform and the superheat of the infiltrating alloy have been studied by Nagata et al[5]. The thermal and mechanical parameters that determine the infiltration process are discussed in the above references.

This fabrication process has been called "squeeze casting" by the manufacturers of automotive engine components[6] who adapted an existing casting process to pressure infiltration of composites. However, composites may also be pressure infiltrated by other processes such as die casting. We have adopted the term "Pressure Casting" to generically refer to any process that involves the hydrostatic application of pressure to the infiltrating liquid metal or alloy. One will note the similarities of this process to other composite processes such as resin transfer molding and glass transfer molding. Indeed, the fluid mechanics are similar if one takes into consideration the viscosity differences of the infiltrating media and such peculiarities as solidification of metals as opposed to curing of resins.

Once the molten alloy has been infiltrated into the fiber preform, it is allowed to solidify. The resulting composite has a microstructure determined by fiber volume fraction, size and distribution. These parameters, along with other parameters such as local solidification time and cooling rate strongly affect the microstructure of the matrix alloy. This paper will focus on this latter aspect of the pressure casting process.

Only a few references on the metallography of the solidification process in metal matrix composites can be found in the open literature. Evidence of a dendritic structure was found in HM3000(carbon fiber)/Cu-8%Sn wire composites[7]. The structure of Al-12%Si was modified by the presence of a fine network of "Saffil" alumina fibers[4]. The Si phase was found to nucleate preferentially on the fiber surface, thus reducing the grain size and leading to a divorced eutectic structure. The authors above also found that the microhardness of the various alloys (Al-4%Cu, Al-10%Mg, Al-12%Si) was markedly increased in reinforced regions. A similar increase in the matrix properties was reported for SiC/6061 Al composites[8]. Causes cited include an increased dislocation or GP zone density[8] or the constraining action of the adjoining fibers[4]. In one study, dispersed graphite particles were found in the interdendritic eutectic regions of Al-Si-Ni alloys[9].

The authors became aware that systematic studies of the solidification process in metal matrix composites were lacking. It seemed obvious that such information would be very useful in relating processing to defect structure, microstructure and properties. This paper is a preliminary summation of a portion of a broader investigation of solidification processing of composite materials.

Materials

Two types of continuous reinforcement are reported in this paper:

1- SCS-2, a 140 micron diameter SiC filament manufactured by AVCO-SMD. The monofilament is CVD deposited onto a 30 micron diameter carbon monofilament core and has a carbon rich surface that promotes bonding and affords protection from strength degradation through liquid metal attack during infiltration[10].

2- Fiber FP, A 20 micron diameter polycrystalline alumina fiber manufactured by DuPont [11]. This fiber was provided in 200 end count tows.

The matrix alloy selected for this study was Al-4.5%Cu. The solidification behavior and microstructure of this alloy has been thoroughly characterized in numerous investigations at the authors' laboratory as well as elsewhere. As such, it is an ideal model alloy for the study of cast composite microstructures. The phase diagram of Al-4.5%Cu displays a eutectic between the alpha Al rich solid solution and the theta (Al_2Cu) phase. Thus, the sequence of solidification is unambiguous and readily interpretable.

Composite specimens were pressure infiltrated and solidified as described in the next section. The resultant microstructures will be discussed in the two following sections.

Experimental

Specimens were consolidated by pressure casting in a laboratory apparatus shown in Figure 1. The apparatus consists of a graphite piston and cylinder enclosed in a dynamically evacuated chamber. The fiber preform and metal are heated to above the alloy liquidus ($650^{\circ}C$). The molten alloy is then pressure infiltrated into the fiber preform by the crosshead drive of an Instron testing machine. Infiltration temperatures and pressures are given in Table I. After infiltration, the apparatus was allowed to cool at a rate of approximately $10^{\circ}C/min$. The samples were then removed from the mold and inspected for soundness. Metallographical sections were polished with diamond paste. The microstructure was revealed by a strongly oxidizing etchant consisting of potassium permanganate, sodium hydroxide and water. Contrast resulted from a combination of selective etching of selective etching of the microstructure and optical interference due to a substrate composition dependent oxide thickness. This technique produces a visual (color) transform of the compositional profile in cast alloys displaying microsegregation.

Table I- Infiltration parameters

Fiber	v/o	T. ($^{\circ}C$)	P(MPa)
SCS-2 (SiC)	44	735	3.5
FP (Al_2O_3)	42	700	8.3

Figure 1 - Schematic of the pressure casting apparatus.

Results

Microstructure Of The Interface

The interface was examined in each system to evaluate the fiber/matrix interactions. The results are as follows:

1. SCS-2 reinforced Al-4.5%Cu interface- A specimen was polished at a low angle to better resolve the interfacial features. Utilizing this technique, features having a thickness of t appear to be magnified by a factor of $\sin \alpha$, where α is the angle between the plane of observation and the fiber axis. Chemical analysis along the line A-B in Figure 2-b was performed by Auger Electron Spectroscopy (AES). The composition profile as determined by AES in scanning is given in Figure 2-c. The electron beam for this investigation was calibrated at 3.5 microns in diameter. This translates to approximately 0.1 micron spacial resolution for the specimen shown in Figure 2-b. Although there may have been some Al_4C_3 formation at the interface, it was not observed in sections such as the one shown in Figure 2-b. The AES scan in Figure 2-c also does not show an interaction zone. We would conclude that the interaction zone, if present, is less than 100 nm in thickness. In similar observations of the interface between the fiber and theta phase, interfacial reactions were not detected.

2. FP (Al_2O_3)/Al-4.5%Cu Interface- Levy et al[12] published data pointing to the existence of an interfacial reaction zone in comocast samples of the lv/o FP/Al4.5%Cu system. In the work reported here the interface was examined by SEM and STEM. Interfaces between the FP fiber and both the alpha and theta matrix phases are shown in Figure 3. These micrographs as well as electron diffraction patterns and microchemical analysis clearly do not reveal an interaction zone between the fiber and either of the matrix phases. Inconsistency may be due to the different processing conditions and fiber volume.

Figure 2-a

Figure 2-b

Figure 2-c

Figure 2- Auger peak to peak ratios on a line scan from A to B across the SCS-2/A1-4.5% Cu interface.

Figure 3- TEM micrographs of Fiber FP/Al-4.5%Cu interface

Microstructure Of The Matrix

1. SCS-2/Al-4.5%Cu Composites- The microstructures of specimens sectioned transverse to the filament axis is shown in Figures 4 through 7. The normal dendritic cast structure can be seen in the unreinforced regions of Figure 4. However, in the presence of fibers, the crystallographic growth habit is disrupted and the dendrite morphology is controlled by the fiber distribution as shown in the reinforced region of Figure 4. The dendrites are no longer defined when the interfiber spacing is smaller than the dendrite arm spacing (in unreinforced sections) by a factor of approximately two as shown in Figure 5. In local regions where the interfiber spaces are larger than the normal dendrite arm spaces, the normal cast structure is again observed as shown in Figure 5. Dendrite arm spacings comparable to those measured in unreinforced regions can be observed in sections cut parallel to the filament axis as shown in Figure 8. The following microstructural features were observed:

- Solute poor regions lie in the center of interfiber regions. Isoconcentrates, as analogued by the color contours, are parallel to the fiber surface. Thus, as the dendrite, or more properly, the growth element approaches the filament surface, the copper concentration increases. These features are especially well revealed in Figure 7.
- The theta phase and therefore the eutectic is found either on the fiber matrix interfacial regions or in the narrow spaces joining two interfiber regions as shown in Figures 6 and 7.
- Microsegregation: The compositional profile across growth elements in the interfiber space shown in Figure 7 was very similar to microprobe traverses across dendrite arms in the unreinforced regions (not shown). The amount of microsegregation was measured for reinforced sections and unreinforced sections by quantitative metallography. A systematic point counting technique was used following the assumptions and guidelines of Hilliard and Cahn[12]. The fiber free dendritic structure is inhomogeneous. Therefore, three differently sectioned areas were used in this analysis. The results are given in Table II.

For the solidification conditions of the above specimen and for that particular fiber geometry, no significant difference was found between segregation in the reinforced and unreinforced regions.

100 μ m

Figure 4- SCS-2/Al-4.5%Cu composite - Section near unreinforced matrix

100 μ m

Figure 5- SCS-2/Al-4.5%Cu composite- Interior section

Figure 6- SCS-2/Al-4.5% Cu composite--SEM micrograph of a transverse section

Figure 7- SCS-2/Al-4.5% Cu composite. Electron microprobe line scan across an interfiber space from A to B in photomicrograph.

Figure 8- Longitudinal cross section of an SCS-2/Al-4.5% Cu composite.

Table II. Quantitative Metallography of an SCS-2 / Al-4.5%Cu composite and Unreinforced Al-4.5%Cu

REGION	NO. POINTS	v/o THETA	STD. DEV.	Wt. % EUTECTIC	POROSITY
Un-reinf matrix	3690	2.2 %	0.25	5.6%	1.0
Re-inforced matrix	9500	2.5	2.5	6.4	2.1

2. Fiber FP(Al_2O_3)/Al-4.5%Cu Composites- The microstructure of this system is very similar to that of the SCS-2 reinforced system discussed above. The theta phase is found predominately around the fibers as shown in Figures 9 and 10. In this case the theta phase has nucleated onto the fiber surface as a divorced eutectic. The larger interfiber spaces are solute poor as shown in Figure 10. However, the extent of microsegregation is strongly influenced by the presence of the fibers. The minimum copper concentration in the alloy is another measure of microsegregation[13]. Table III gives the minimum minimum of a series of electron microprobe traverses across dendrite arms in the case of the unreinforced matrix and across interfiber regions in the case of composites cast under identical conditions. The minimum concentration is higher in the composite than in the unreinforced matrix.

Figure 9- Fiber FP/Al-4.5% Cu composite

Figure 10- Electron microprobe line scans across an interfiber region of a Fiber FP/Al-4.5% Cu composite.

Table III. Minimum copper contents in Fiber FP/Al 4.5%Cu system

<u>REGION</u>	<u>NO. DATA POINTS</u>	<u>MIN. Cu CONC.FOUND</u>	<u>DENDRITE ARM/INTER FIBER SPACING</u>	<u>SOLIDIFICATION TIME - sec</u>
Unreinf. matrix	370	1.78 wt %	105 μ m	848 s
Com-posite	330	2.85	65	825

As an added confirmation of the above observations, differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) was employed. Samples of the fiber-free matrix and of the composite materials were cooled at a constant rate after remelting. The heat dissipated was recorded as a function of temperature. A typical DSC experiment is shown in Figure 11. The peaks shown correspond to the heat of fusion liberated during solidification of the alpha phase and the eutectic plus alpha peak area can be used to obtain a qualitative measurement of the fraction eutectic. Peak ratio data are given in Table IV.

Figure 11- Differential Scanning Calorimetry cooling curves for a 42 v/o Fiber FP(alumina)/ Al-4.5% Cu composite

Table IV- DSC peak area ratios for Fiber FP/Al-4.5% Cu composites and the unreinforced matrix alloy

SAMPLE	COOLING RATE K/min	DSC EUTECTIC PEAK FRACTION
Matrix	7	0.080
Matrix	7	0.074
44v/o SCS-2 composite	7	0.064
42v/o Fiber FP composite	7	0.020
Matrix	20	0.082
39v/o Fiber FP composite	20	0.050
46v/o Fiber FP composite	20	0.038

Discussion

The grain size of the matrix was not reduced by the presence of the fibers. Thus, the fiber surface does not act as a heterogeneous nucleation catalyst for the primary solid solution alpha phase for the conditions studied here. However, in other experiments utilizing TiC sintered surface compacts infiltrated by the same alloy, nucleation did occur on the TiC surface under similar processing conditions. (TiC is reported to be a nucleation catalyst for aluminum[16].)

The minimum copper concentration is found in the center of the inter-fiber spaces which is therefore the site of initial solidification. Growth of the alpha phase progresses toward the fiber surfaces where the solute is enriched. The growing solid appears to avoid the fibers. Several mechanisms could be responsible:

- Surface energy considerations point to one possibility. Since heterogeneous nucleation has not taken place on the fiber surfaces,

$$S_{f1} + S_{1s} < S_{fs}$$

where S_{f1} = fiber-liquid surface energy
 S_{1s} = liquid-solid surface energy
 S_{fs} = fiber-solid surface energy,

there is a driving force for the solid to avoid the fiber surface. This effect is similar to the "particle pushing" effect found during solidification of certain melts containing inclusions[18] and is probably responsible for the microstructures noted with injected graphite particles[9]. However, these forces have a relatively short range effect[17] and could not account for the coring patterns that are observed here to form isoconcentrates that contours the fiber surface.

- Differences in thermal properties between fiber and matrix is another possible explanation. The growing solid must dissipate the heat of fusion

that is generated at the interface. The fibers, having a lower thermal diffusivity and higher heat capacity might be expected to cool more slowly than the matrix and to be slightly warmer. The liquid at the interface would then be the last to solidify.

- Accumulation of solute at the fiber surface, thus diverting the growing solid to other regions where the solute concentration is lower.

We do not at present have sufficient evidence to determine unambiguously the mechanism that produces the coring patterns observed here. It is most likely that solute diffusion is primarily responsible for the observed microstructures since the thermal profile is essentially flat at the low cooling rates observed here. The final answer will await detailed analysis of many specimens solidified at different cooling rates and volume fractions of reinforcement.

One of the most important observations presented here relating to the development of a metal matrix composite casting technology is the lesser microsegregation in the higher volume fraction composites composed of finer diameter fibers than in the unreinforced matrix alloy. The question remains as to why microsegregation is reduced in FP(alumina) reinforced composites more extensively than in the larger diameter SiC reinforced composites. The extent of microsegregation in solidification varies with the extent of solid state and liquid state diffusion. The upperbound amount of microsegregation can be predicted by the Scheill equation and the lower bound amount is given by equilibrium solidification (lever rule)[18]. The critical parameter, N , is given by

$$N = 4t/d^2$$

where t is the solidification time and d is the dendrite arm spacing. From this parameter the extent of microsegregation can be deduced for an assumed dendrite geometry[14]. Agreement with experimental data is excellent[15] provided that appropriate geometric corrections have been applied to the dendrite arm spacing ($d_c = 0.32d$) to account for the real dendrite geometry.

If the dendrite arm spacing for a given solidification time is artificially reduced, N will increase and the extent of microsegregation will decrease. From a physical point of view, the shorter the distance over which diffusion must take place, the more complete homogenization will be. The inference is that the geometrical arrangement of the fibers limits the diffusion distance to the restricted interfiber spaces.

The smallest measured dendrite arm spacing found in the matrix adjacent to the SiC reinforced composite was 70 μm . This value is approximately equal to the size of the interfiber space transverse to the fiber axis during solidification after infiltration in the pressure casting facility used in this study. Thus, the effect on microsegregation as compared to the unreinforced matrix was minimal. However, the same dendrite arm spacing was significantly larger than the interfiber spacing in the FP alumina reinforced composites (see Figure 9 and Table III). The minimum Cu content was found in a loosely packed area of the specimen with an interfiber spacing of approximately 65 μm . Taking $t = 825$ sec as measured, we calculate a minimum copper concentration of 2.6wt% utilizing the t_c correction discussed above. Similarly, using $t = 848$ sec as measured for the unreinforced specimen and a dendrite arm spacing d of 105 μm , we calculate a minimum copper concentration of 1.6 wt% [14]. The observed values are given in Table III and are in agreement within experimental error. We can reach the preliminary conclusion that the finer the fiber, the more marked the effect will be. In the case of a finer fiber such as the 3 μm saffil, the matrix alloy may be essentially free of microsegregation. This may be the cause of the property improvements noted in

reference 6. The differential scanning calorimetry data given in table IV is an additional confirmation of the above speculation since:

- As the fiber diameter decreases, the eutectic peak and therefore the amount of eutectic decreases.

- As the cooling rate is increased, the amount of eutectic is increased. For the same diffusion distance, there is less time for homogenization to take place.

- As the fiber volume fraction is increased, the amount of eutectic decreases (since the interfiber spacing has decreased).

Conclusions

1- Fiber FP(alumina) and SCS-2(SiC) preforms were successfully infiltrated by Al-4.5%Cu.

2- Interfacial reactions between either of these fibers and the matrix were not observed.

3- When the dendrite arm spacing is larger than the interfiber spacing by a factor of approximately 2, the dendritic microstructure becomes ill defined.

4- Neither of the fibers studied here acted as heterogeneous nucleation catalyst. Therefore, the grain size was not reduced.

5- Growth of the solid phase progressed toward the fiber surfaces from the center of the interfiber spaces. As a consequence, the copper concentration increases near the fiber surface. The eutectic tends to solidify adjacent to the fiber surfaces.

6- Microsegregation is reduced when the interfiber spacing is smaller than the dendrite arm spacing in the unreinforced matrix at similar solidification times. This is due to increased back diffusion of the solute in the solid phase during and after solidification.

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